

Ethnognocological Plant Diversity among Rural Women at Niwari District Madhya Pradesh

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Abstract

Ethnognocology is emerging branch of ethanobotany present work focused on 10 gynecological diseases very common among the women of this district. During study there have been four sites selected Niwari, Prithvipur, Orchha and Bangaw. 100 plants studied out of which herb 34, shrub 17, trees 34, climber 09, Aerial roots 02, parasite 01, underground and plant part have been studied total 46 family plants studies. During study it has been found that allopathic medicines of all these diseases have their own side effect but ethno medicinal plants have no such any side effect.

Keywords

Ethnomedicinal Plants, Madhya Pradesh, Rural Tribal, Gynic disorder.

Introduction

Gynecological disorders are a group of medical conditions that effect the female reproductive system. These conditions can be caused by a variety of factors such hormonal imbalance genetic disorders, infection and physiological irregularities they can range from mild to severe and can significantly effect a women's health and quality of life. Due to pollution, atmosphere pressure, social pressure, present time women are facing many health issues.

Due to pollution and work pressure there are so many hormonal problem's which effect endocrinal system to women are available in society due to lack knowledge and money the women of this district suffering from many gynic disorder abortion, delivery pain, easy delivery, improve fertility, lactation heavy bleeding, leucorrhoea, menstrual, disorder, menopause, prolapse uterus. Women's of this district suffering from many gynic disorders butin present study most common Ten disease, and identification of plant species have been done with the help of old ladies Aya's, Vaidya, Ojhas and Hakeemis.

Four sites [Niwari (A), Prithvipur(B), Orchha (C), Bangaw (D)] have been selected for study and different age group of women who were suffering from gynic disorder. On the basis of past history and uses of ethnomedicinal plant part. Survey have been done and listing of plant used in gynic disorder from Jan. 2022 to 2025 June. During study at four sites a practical had been done on women of all ages and it was concluded that out of all the several plants that had been tested *Dalbergia-sissoo* turned out to be the most effective on heavy bleeding during mensuration. Or any type of gynic disorder related with heavy bleeding. This plant is also effective in any hormonal problems.

In the study period there are (100) plants belonging to (46) families are maximum number of plant present in family *fabaceae* (10) and less

number of plants belong *Amaranthaceae*, *Aloeaceae*, *Anacardiaceae*, *Arecaceae*, *Apiaceae*, *Asteraceae*, *Acanthaceae*, *Aristolochiaceae*, *Asclepiadaceae*, *Apocynaceae*, *Brassicaceae*, *Caricaceae*, *Cucurbitaceae*, *Cappardaceae*, *Convolvulaceae*, *Combretaceae*, *Euphorbiaceae*, *Fabaceae*, *Gentianaceae*, *Liliaceae*, *Lamiaceae*, *Leguminaceae*, *Malvaceae*, *Myrtaceae*, *Melastomataceae*, *Moringaceae*, *Moraceae*, *Menispermaceae*, *Minosaceae*, *Nyctagenaceae*, *Oxalidaceae*, *Punicaceae*, *Palmeaceae*, *Poaceae*, *Rutaceae*, *Rubiaceae*, *Rhamnaceae*, *Rosaceae*, *Solanaceae*, *Sapindaceae*, *Sterculiaceae*, *Urticaceae*, *Vitaceae*, *Violaceae*, *Zingiberaceae*, *Zygophyllaceae*.

Types of diseases, abortion, delivery pain, easy delivery, heavy bleeding, improve fertility, lactation, leucorrhea, menstrual disorders, menopause and prolapse uterus, studied during study period. All these diseases are most common in the district. Symptoms of gynic disorder also studied and some allopathic medicines provided to cure many gynecological disorder with their many side effect also given in this study and how ethnomedicinal plants are effective to cure these diseases without any side effect.

Objective of study

1. Total number of plants used in different diseases at all sites.
2. Route of medicine to cure gynic disorders.
3. Mode of administration to cure different disorders.
4. Different part used of women to cure different disorders.

5. Number of plants habitat used to cure gynec disorders.

Review of Literature

Ethnomedicinal work have been done by Arjariya et al., (2009), Kiritikar et al., (2001), Lone et al., (2008), Dixit and Pandey (1984), Sinha and Dogra (1985), Rai et al., (2000), Koli et al., (2002), Saxena et al., (2002), Mahbubur et al., (2013), Singhariya et al., (2023), so the present work focused on this problem because this district is full of phytodiversity 100 medicinal plants are related with gynec disorder.

Ethnogaecology is an emerging discipline deals with various disease among women in tribal societies, related to sterility conception and abortion etc (Singharia, 2023).

Methodology

The study was conducted during 2022-25 covering the area of bank of river Betwa at Niwari Prithvipur, Orchha, Bangaw village. The plants related gynec disorder are given here. The method adopted in the study was interviewing and observation of plant used specific questions based asked and the information were recorded in the ethnobotanical filed Jain et al., (1995). Based on the information plants arranged with their local name, botanical name, family plant part, used diseases and ethnomedicinal gynec uses are reported. Niwari district are reported. Niwari district was originally part of Tikamgarh district but was separated and established as a new district on 1st Oct. 2018.

The previous history, dosage plant part used to treat diseases, type of diseases information about plant and other detail related with gynec disorder a part from the collection of plants for their day to day ailments. is of great importance. Field trip and collection of information from gynec disorder suffering women., Work is manly based on extensive and intensive field survey of different selected villages.

In qualitative study by using plant part on women on the basis of symptoms. The qualitative study will be done that how many women suffering from gynec disorder.

Study Area Niwari district located at central part of Bundelkhand region at 23°10 to 25°20 North latitude and 78°59 to 80°26 East longitude belonging at 150 to 300 MSL. It is situated at Jhansi Chhatarpur National Highway 39. It is 35 kilometer away from Jhansi. The river Betwa surrounded boundary of Niwari district. It was formerly part of Tikamgarh district. It is adjacent Jhansi and Niwari district of M.P.

Field trip and collection of information from gynec disorder suffering women, work is manly based on extensive and intensive field survey of different selected villages. There are two main tools for ethnomedicinal study. To get information from traditional heal the practitioners a questionnaire (datasheet) must be produced.

Questionnaire :

1. Name of informant-
2. Sex
3. Age
4. Name of Village-
5. Occupation-
6. Address-
7. Name of Disease-
8. Vernacular name-
9. Botanical name-
10. Family -
11. Locality-
12. Habit-
13. Plant parts used as Medicines -
14. How a plant part used-
15. Method of preparation for use-
16. Mode of administration-
17. Route of medicines-
18. Dosage-
19. Any other comment-
20. Effect after ethnomedicinal use-

Result and Discussion

The present study revealed that 100 plant species belonging to 46 families used by the local healers against gynecological problems of women are documented, out of 100

plants. India is very rich in two main components of ethnomedicinal wealth and vegetation. The present work based on ethnogynocological plant diversity among rural Women at Niwari District M.P.

Table 1 : Total Number of plants used in different disease at all sites during (2022-2025)

S. No.	Name of Diseases	Number of plants
1.	Abortion	13
2.	Delivery pain	07
3.	Easy delivery	07
4.	Heavy bleeding	07
5.	Improve fertility	05
6.	Lactation	12
7.	Leucorrhea	25
8.	Menstrual disorder	25
9.	Menopause	05
10.	Prolapse uterus	05

Oral administration of plant medicine was the most typical method, out of some plant species, were used to treat Abortion (13), Delivery pain (abdominal/Labor pain) (7), Easy delivery (7), Heavy bleeding (7), Improve fertility/infertility (5), Lactation (12),Leucorrhea(25), Menstrual disorder (25), Menopause (5), Prolapse uterus (5) and other diseases etc.

Fig. Major diseases cured through ethnomedicinal plants.

Table - 1

Name of Diseases	Botanical Name	Local Name/ Family	Habit	Part used
Abortion	<i>Abrus-precatorius</i>	Gumchi (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Climber	Seed, Root, Leaves
Easy delivery	<i>Achranthus-aspera</i>	Chirchita (<i>Amaranthaceae</i>)	Herb	Root, Flower
Delivery pain	<i>Aegle-marmelos</i>	Bel (<i>Rutaceae</i>)	Tree	Fruit, Bark, Leaf, Root
Abortion	<i>Annona-squamosa</i>	Sitaphala (<i>Annonaceae</i>)	Shrub	Seed
Lactation	<i>Asparagus-officinalis</i>	Seetmuli (<i>Liliaceae</i>)	Climber	Shoot
Prolapse uterus	<i>Asparagus-recemsus</i>	Satavar (<i>Liliaceae</i>)	Climber	Root, Seed
Heavy Bleeding	<i>Authocephalus-cadamba</i>	Cadamba (<i>Rubiaceae</i>)	Tree	Stem, Bark
Delivery Pain	<i>Bombax-cieba</i>	Semal (<i>Malvaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark Stem
Abortion	<i>Butea-monosperma</i>	Palash (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark
Leucorrhoea-	<i>Calotropis-</i>	Aak	Herb	Root
Easy Delivery Pain	<i>gigantean</i>	(<i>Asclepiadaceae</i>)		
Easy Delivery Pain	<i>Cardia-dichotoma</i>	Kasmar (<i>Etheretiaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark
Abortion	<i>Carica-papaya</i>	Papaya (<i>Caricaceae</i>)	Shrub	Fruit, unripe fruit
Abortion	<i>Caryota-urens</i>	Ban Khajoor (<i>Palmeaceae</i>)	Tree	Root
Abortion	<i>Cassia-tora</i>	Chikonda (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed
Leucorrhoea	<i>Chenopodium-album</i>	Bathua (<i>Chenopodiaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed, Leaf, Stem, Root
Menstrual Disorder	<i>Cissus quadrangulariss</i>	Harjora (<i>Vitaceae</i>)	Climber	Seed
Easy	<i>Citrullus-colocynthis</i>	Kakora (<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>)	Herb	Fruits
Prolapse Uterus	<i>Curcuma-longa</i>	Haldi (<i>Zingiberaceae</i>)	Herb	Whole plant
Heavy Bleedings	<i>Cynodon-dactylon</i>	Durba (<i>Poaceae</i>)	Herb	Stem
Heavy Bleeding	<i>Dalbergia-sissoo</i>	Shisham (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Tree	Leaves, Root
Delivery Pain	<i>Desmost achyabipinnata</i>	Kasghas (<i>Poaceae</i>)	Herb, halgrass	Root

Improve Fertility	<i>Duccus-carota</i>	Gajor (Apiaceae)	Under-ground stem	Stem
Heavy Bleeding	<i>Eupatorrium-cannabinum</i>	Kalijhar (Asteraceae)	Herb	Leaves
Lactation	<i>Euphorbia-hirta</i>	Dudhi (Euphorbiaceae)	Herb	Latex
Improve Fertility	<i>Ficus-religiosa</i>	Pepal (Moraceae)	Tree	Bark, Fruit
Lactation	<i>Foeniculam-vulgare</i>	Saunf (Apiaceae)	Herb	Leaves
Leucorrhoea	<i>Lycopersicon-esculentum</i>	Tomato (Solanaceae)	Herb, Tree	Fruit
Easy Delivery	<i>Mentha-spicata L.</i>	Podina	Herb	Leaves
Abortion	<i>Moringa-olefera</i>	Sahjan (Moringaceae)	Tree	Root, Bark
Delivery Pain	<i>Osimumsanctum</i>	Tulsi (Lamiaceae)	Herb	Leaf
Improve Fertility	<i>Phyllanthus-emblica</i>	Amla (Euphorbiaceae)	Shrab	Seed fruit
Leucorrhoea	<i>Punica-granatum</i>	Anar (Punicaceae)	Shrub	Flower
Improve Fertility	<i>Putranjiva-roxburghii</i>	Putranjiva (Euphorbiaceae)	Tree	Seed, Leaves
Prolapse Uterus	<i>Saccharum-officinatum</i>	Gud (Poaceae)	Herb	Jaggery
Delivery Pain	<i>Trachyspermum-ammi</i>	Azwain (Apiaceae)	Herb	Seed, Leaf
Leucorrhoea	<i>Tribuls-terrestris</i>	Gokhru (Zygophyllaceae)	Annual Tree	Fruit
Delivery Pain	<i>Trigonella-foenum-graecum</i>	Methi (Fabaceae)	Herb	Seed
Improve Fertility	<i>Withania-somnifera</i>	Ashwagandha (Solanaceae)	Herb	Root
Delivery Pain	<i>Zizyphus-mauritina Lam</i>	Ber (Phamnaceae)	Shrub	Stem, Bark

Table 2: Route of medicine to cure gynec disorder (2022-2025)

S. No.	Type	Number of plants
1.	Water	06
2.	Honey	03
3.	Ghee	01
4.	Milk	10
5.	Oil	02
6.	Jaggery	02
7.	Sugar candy	03
8.	Mixed with other plant part	10

Water (6), Honey (3), Ghee (1), Milk (10), Oil (2), Jaggery (2), Sugar candy (3), mixed with plant part (10) etc.

Fig. Route of Medicine to cure gynec disorder.

Table- 2

Route of Medicine	Botanical Name	Local Name/ Family	Habit	Part used
Water	<i>Azadirachta-indica</i>	Neem (<i>Meliaceae</i>)	Tree	Leaves, Bark
Water	<i>Asparagus-officinalis</i>	Seetmuli (<i>Liliaceae</i>)	Climber	Shoot
Water	<i>Bombax-cieba</i>	Semal (<i>Malvaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark Stem
Jaggery	<i>Curcuma-longa</i>	Haldi (<i>Zingiberaceae</i>)	Herb	Whole plant
Milk	<i>Ficus-bengalensis</i>	Bargad (<i>Moraceae</i>)	Tree	Bark, Seed, Latex
Water	<i>Moringa-olefera</i>	Sahjan (<i>Moringaceae</i>)	Tree	Root, Bark
Milk	<i>Osimumsanctum</i>	Tulsi (<i>Lamiaceae</i>)	Herb	Leaf
Honey	<i>Punica-granatum</i>	Anar (<i>Punicaceae</i>)	Shrub	Flower
Water	<i>Trigonella-foenum-graecum</i>	Methi (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed
Water	<i>Trachyspermum-ammi</i>	Azwain (<i>Apiaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed, Leaf

Table - 3 Mode of Administration to cure different disorder (During 2022-2025)

S. No.	Mode of Administration	Number of plants
1.	Powder	20
2.	Paste	12
3.	Decoction	06
4.	Juice	05
5.	Externally use massage	05
6.	Fumigant	05
7.	Chewing	07

The four type of medicinal preparation in the current survey were used by grinding up diverse plant parts into powder (20), paste (12), Decoction (6), Juice (5), Externally use massage (5), fumiga (5), Chewing (7) etc.

Fig. Mode of Drug preparation.

Table- 3

Mode of Administration	Botanical Name	Local Name/ Family	Habit	Part used
Paste	<i>Amaranthus-spinosus</i>	Chorai (<i>Amaranthaceae</i>)	Herb	Whole plant
Paste	<i>Annona-squamosa</i>	Sitaphal (<i>Annonaceae</i>)	Shrub	Seed
Powder	<i>Asparagus-officinalis</i>	Seetmuli (<i>Liliaceae</i>)	Climber	Shoot
Powder	<i>Bombax-cieba</i>	Semal (<i>Malvaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark Stem
Powder	<i>Cardia-dichotoma</i>	Kasmar (<i>Etheretiaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark
Powder	<i>Carissa-spinarum</i>	Jangle-Karonda (<i>Apocynaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark
Powder	<i>Cassia-tora</i>	Chikonda (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed
Powder	<i>Curcuma-longa</i>	Haldi (<i>Zingiberaceae</i>)	Herb	Whole plant
Paste	<i>Duccus-carota</i>	Gajor (<i>Apiaceae</i>)	Underground stem	Stem
Juice	<i>Ghritk-umarri</i>	Aloevera (<i>Liliaceae</i>)	Herb	Leaf
Powder	<i>Nyctanthes-arbortristis</i>	Parijat (<i>Nyctaginaceae</i>)	Shrub	Leaves
Powder	<i>Phyllanthus-simplex Retz.</i>	Roli (<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>)	Herb	Leaves
Powder	<i>Ricinus-communis</i>	Arandi (<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>)	Shrub	Leaves
Powder	<i>Schleichera-oleosa</i>	Kosum (<i>Sapindaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark
Decoction	<i>Spondias-pinnata</i>	Deshi Amra (<i>Anacardiaceae</i>)	Shrub	Bark
Paste	<i>Zizyphus-mauritina Lam</i>	Ber (<i>Phamnaceae</i>)	Shrub	Stem, Bark

Table- 4 Different part used of women to cure different disorders (During 2022-2025)

S. No.	Name of Plant	Number of plants
1.	Root	27
2.	Whole plant	04
3.	Seed	23
4.	Stem	11
5.	Fruit	10
6.	Bark	15
7.	Flower	05
8.	Leaves	29
9.	Latex	03
10.	Bud	02

The majority of medications are made from the following plant parts : Root (27), Whole plant (4), Seed (23), Stem (11), Fruit (10), Bark (15), Flower (5), Leaves (29), Latex (3), Bud (2) etc.

Fig. Medications are made from the following plant parts

Table- 4

Botanical Name	Local Name/ Family	Habit	Part used
<i>Abrus-precatorius</i>	Gumchi (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Climber	Seed, Root, Leaves
<i>Abutilon-indicum</i>	Kanghi (<i>Malvaceae</i>)	Tree	Seed, Root, Leaves
<i>Acacia-catechu</i>	Khair (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Shrub	Stem, Bark
<i>Aegle-marmelos</i>	Bel (<i>Rutaceae</i>)	Tree	Fruit, Bark, Leaf, Root
<i>Amaranthus-spinosus</i>	Chorai (<i>Amaranthaceae</i>)	Herb	Whole plant
<i>Annona-squamosa</i>	Sitaphal (<i>Annonaceae</i>)	Shrub	Seed
<i>Asparagus-recemsus</i>	Satavar (<i>Liliaceae</i>)	Climber	Root, Seed
<i>Bombax-cieba</i>	Semal (<i>Malvaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark Stem
<i>Carica-papaya</i>	Papaya (<i>Caricaceae</i>)	Shrub	Fruit, unripe fruit
<i>Chenopodium-album</i>	Bathua (<i>Chenopodiaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed, Leaf, Stem, Root
<i>Cissus-quadranulariss</i>	Harjora (<i>Vitaceae</i>)	Climber	Seed
<i>Citoria-ternatea</i>	Aprajita (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Climber	Root

<i>Cnicus-benedictus</i>	Blessed thistle (<i>Asteraceae</i>)	Whole plant	Leaf, Stem
<i>Coriandram-sativum</i>	Dhaniya (<i>Limiaceae</i>)	Annual herb	Seed
<i>Curcuma-longa</i>	Haldi (<i>Zingiberaceae</i>)	Herb	Whole plant
<i>Dalbergia-sissoo</i>	Shisham (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Tree	Leaves, Root
<i>Diplocyclos-palmatus</i>	Shivlinghi (<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>)	Climber	Seed
<i>Duccus-carota</i>	Gajor (<i>Apiaceae</i>)	Under-ground stem	Stem
<i>Ghritk-umarri</i>	Aloevera (<i>Liliaceae</i>)	Herb	Leaf
<i>Lycopersicon-esculentum</i>	Tomato (<i>Solanaceae</i>)	Herb, Tree	Fruit
<i>Moringa-olefera</i>	Sahjan (<i>Moringaceae</i>)	Tree	Root, Bark
<i>Osimumsanctum</i>	Tulsi (<i>Lamiaceae</i>)	Herb	Leaf
<i>Phyllanthus-emblica</i>	Amla (<i>Euphor biaceae</i>)	Shrab	Seed fruit
<i>Punica-granatum</i>	Anar (<i>Punicaceae</i>)	Shrub	Flower
<i>Putranzjiva-roxburghii</i>	Putranjiva (<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>)	Tree	Seed, Leaves
<i>Saraca-indica</i>	Ashok (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark, leaves
<i>Trachyspermum-ammi</i>	Azwain (<i>Apiaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed, Leaf
<i>Tribuls-terrestris</i>	Gokhru (<i>Zygophyllaceae</i>)	Annual Tree	Fruit
<i>Trigonella-foenum-graecum</i>	Methi (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed
<i>Verbena-officinalis</i>	Shomakay (<i>Verbenaceae</i>)	Shrub	Whole plant

Table 5 : Number of plant habitat used to cure gynec disorders (During 2022-2025)

S.No.	Name of plant	Number of plants
1.	Herb	34
2.	Shrub	17
3.	Trees	34
4.	Climber	09
5.	Arial roots	02
6.	Parasite (Stem)	02
7.	Epiphyte	01
8.	Underground plant part	01

The present study revealed that 100 plant species belonging to 48 families used by the local healers against gynecological problems of women are documented. The majority of the species are Shrubs (17), followed by herbs (34), Tree (34) and Climbers (9), Arial roots (02) Parasite (02), Epiphyte (01), Underground plant part (01).

Fig. Life form of reported flora

Table- 5

Botanical Name	Local Name/ Family	Habit	Part used
<i>Aegle-marmelos</i>	Bel (<i>Rutaceae</i>)	Tree	Fruit, Bark, Leaf, Root
<i>Authocephalus-cadamba</i>	Cadamba (<i>Rubiaceae</i>)	Tree	Stem, Bark
<i>Achranthus-aspera</i>	Chirchita (<i>Amaranthaceae</i>)	Herb	Root, Flower
<i>Amaranthus-spinosus</i>	Chorai (<i>Amaranthaceae</i>)	Herb	Whole plant
<i>Abrus-precatorius</i>	Gumchi (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Climber	Seed, Root, Leaves
<i>Abutilon-indicum</i>	Kanghi (<i>Malvaceae</i>)	Tree	Seed, Root, Leaves
<i>Accatia-cuttachu</i>	Khair (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Shrub	Stem, Bark
<i>Azadirachta-indica</i>	Neem (<i>Meliaceae</i>)	Tree	Leaves, Bark
<i>Asparagus-recemsus</i>	Satavar (<i>Liliaceae</i>)	Climber	Root, Seed
<i>Asparagus-officinalis</i>	Seetmuli (<i>Liliaceae</i>)	Climber	Shoot
<i>Annona-squamosa</i>	Sitaphal (<i>Annonaceae</i>)	Shrub	Seed
<i>Bauhinia-varigata</i>	Kachnar (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Small tree	Flower buds powder
<i>Butea-monosperma</i>	Palash (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark
<i>Borhavia-diffusa</i>	Punarnava (<i>Nyctaginaceae</i>)	Herb	Root
<i>Calotropis-gigantean</i>	Aak (<i>Asclepiadaceae</i>)	Herb	Root
<i>Chenopodium-album</i>	Bathua (<i>Chenopodiaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed, Leaf, Stem, Root
<i>Caryota-urens</i>	Ban Khajoor (<i>Palmeaceae</i>)	Tree	Root
<i>Coculus species</i>	Chharanta (<i>Menispermaceae</i>)	Climber	Leaves

<i>Cassia-tora</i>	Chikonda (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed
<i>Coriandram-sativum</i>	Dhaniya (<i>Limiaceae</i>)	Annual herb	Seed
<i>Cynodon-dactylon</i>	Durba (<i>Poaceae</i>)	Herb	Stem
<i>Curcuma-longa</i>	Haldi (<i>Zingiberaceae</i>)	Herb	Whole plant
<i>Cardia-dichotoma</i>	Kasmar (<i>Etheriaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark
<i>Citrullus-colocynthis</i>	Kakora (<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>)	Herb	Fruits
<i>Convolvulus-arvensis</i>	Morning glory (<i>Convolvulaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed
<i>Diplocyclos-palmatus</i>	Shivlinghi (<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>)	Climber	Seed
<i>Duccus-carota</i>	Gajor (<i>Apiaceae</i>)	Under- ground stem	Stem
<i>Dalbergia-sissoo</i>	Shisham (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Tree	Leaves, Root
<i>Datura-metel</i> Linn	Kala Dhatura (<i>Solanaceae</i>)	Herb	Leaves, Seed
<i>Euphorbia-hirta</i>	Dudhi (<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>)	Herb	Latex
<i>Ficus-bengalensis</i>	Bargad (<i>Moraceae</i>)	Tree	Bark, Seed, Latex
<i>Ficus-racemosa</i>	Omar (<i>Moraceae</i>)	Tree	Fruit
<i>Ficus-religiosa</i>	Pepal (<i>Moraceae</i>)	Tree	Bark, Fruit
<i>Foeniculam-vulgare</i>	Sauf (<i>Apiaceae</i>)	Herb	Leaves
<i>Ghritk-umarri</i>	Aloevera (<i>Liliaceae</i>)	Herb	Leaf
<i>Lycopersicon-esculentum</i>	Tomato (<i>Solanaceae</i>)	Herb, Tree	Fruit
<i>Momordica-charantia</i> L.	Karela (<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>)	Herb	Root
<i>Moringa-olefera</i>	Sahjan (<i>Moringaceae</i>)	Tree	Root, Bark
<i>Nyctanthes-arbortristis</i>	Parijat (<i>Nyctaginaceae</i>)	Shrub	Leaves
<i>Osimum-sanctum</i>	Tulsi (<i>Lamiaceae</i>)	Herb	Leaf
<i>Phyllanthus-emblica</i>	Amla (<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>)	Shrub	Seed fruit
<i>Punica-granatum</i>	Anar (<i>Punicaceae</i>)	Shrub	Flower
<i>Putranzjiva-roxburghii</i>	Putranjiva (<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>)	Tree	Seed, Leaves
<i>Ricinus-communis</i>	Arandi (<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>)	Shrub	Leaves
<i>Saraca-indica</i>	Ashok (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Tree	Bark, leaves
<i>Trigonella-foenum-graecum</i>	Methi (<i>Fabaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed
<i>Tribuls-terrestris</i>	Gokhru (<i>Zygophyllaceae</i>)	Annual Tree	Fruit
<i>Trachyspermum-ammi</i>	Azwain (<i>Apiaceae</i>)	Herb	Seed, Leaf
<i>Tinospora-cordifolia</i>	Guduchi (<i>Menispermaceae</i>)	Climber	Root
<i>Tribuls-terrestris</i>	Markundi (<i>Zygophyllaceae</i>)	Herb	Leaves
<i>Withania-somnifera</i>	Ashwagandha (<i>Solanaceae</i>)	Herb	Root
<i>Zizyphus-mauritina</i> Lam	Ber (<i>Phamnaceae</i>)	Shrub	Stem, Bark

The present study revealed that 100 plant Panduranga et al., (2011), Vidhyasgar and Murthy et al., (2012), Vineeta et al., (2022), Jaiom et al., (2022) all study have been done on Ethnobotanical plant diversity among rural Women at Niwari District M.P.

Fig - Number of species belonging to families reported in this study

Conclusion

1. In present study ten gynec disorder are very common in all sites are abortion, delivery pain, easy delivery, heavy bleeding, infertility, lactation, leucorrhea, menstrual disorder, menopause and prolapse uterus. There are many plants which have ethnomedicinal importance to cure many diseases, but in present study with the help of questionnaire
2. This research aims to explore the potential of ethnomedicinal plants in managing common gynecological disorders menstrual disorder (PCOD heavy bleeding in early age, and at the age of menopause) infertility, leucorrhea, lactation, hormonal imbalance and prolapse uterus etc. Women play a pivotal role in both family dynamics and professional growth, but today modern life style come out as main factors that have led to rise in gynecological disorder due family, society work place and environmental pressure, conventional allopathic treatment provide quick relief rather than a complete cure that leads to long term health challenges.
3. Hence it is very challenging in modern time how can protect floristic diversity of study sites permanently but improvement in conservation policies can prevent from it.
4. The present study is an attempt to aware how ethnomedicinal plants are useful for women without given any side effect. During study different plant part, different mode of administration, different route of medicines, different habitat of Ethnomedicinal plant have been studied.
5. Niwari district is smallest district of M.P. but famous and rich in floristic diversity. There is very little knowledge of ethnomedicinal plant and how can use

ethnomedicinal plants to check gynec disorder of the district hence, a decent platform can be prepared to go into deep study of such subject.

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